

Predators in Orchids

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IT WAS THE middle of the 1970s. A group of Indonesians and one American were making their way up Mount Salak (“salak” means “lizard”; the mountain — or maybe a big hill — looks like one) near the famed Bogor Botanical Gardens (“Kebun Raya Indonesia”; “kebun” means “garden” and “raya” is “big”). The American saw what looked like a *Corybas* species under a tree and started to crawl toward it. One of the Indonesians yanked him back immediately: “Don’t even do that again you ‘orang puti gila’ (‘orang,’ ‘man’; ‘puti,’ ‘white’; ‘gila,’ ‘crazy’; a nickname given to the American because he loves spicy, hot Indonesian food and smelly durian fruit, both of which sane orang puti seldom do, if ever), cobras lurk near these flowers.”

The orang puti gila believed his Indonesian friend, pulled away, and lived to coauthor this article. At the time, he wondered why a cobra would lurk near a small orchid. Eventually, he found out. Snakes lurk near or in (Fig. 1A) orchids to prey on pollinating vectors (Fig. 1B) or predate on the pollinators (Fig. 1C).

In Colombia, the poisonous pit viper, *Bothrops atrox*, also known as the common lancehead, barba amarilla, mapepire balsain or fer-de-lance (which is also the name of the first novel about orchid-loving detective Nero Wolfe, written by Rex Stout in 1934), hides near the yellow flowers of *Elleanthus longibracteatus* and preys on hummingbirds (Fig. 1B) that visit them (Ospina 1969), probably as pollinators (Nunes et al. 2016). Another pit viper, *Trimeresurus purpureomaculatus*, the mangrove pit viper, was photographed hiding inside a *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* plant (Fig. 1A). It is not clear if the snake just happened to be there, was only resting, perhaps sheltering or hiding temporarily in the orchid, or if it was in the plant to prey on visitors. The changeable lizard, *Calotes versicolor* (Fig. 1C, black arrow), may have only passed through or may have been in the plant to prey on pollinating or other visiting insects.

A snake was also photographed slithering over a white *Phalaenopsis* flower but it is not clear if, like the pit

vipers above, this snake routinely visits the orchid and happened to be on the inflorescence when the photographer noticed it and recorded the event, or if the photograph was posed.

In any case, snakes do slither into orchid gardens. The orang puti gila was at Maryland Orchids in Singapore in the early 1980s when the workers found and killed a black cobra. One reason for the attraction of snakes to orchids is mice or rats that may eat parts of the plants. The

[1] Snakes and a lizard in or near orchids.

A. Mangrove pit viper, in a *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* plant in Singapore. **B.** A fer-de-lance pit viper, *Bothrops atrox* (**d**) lurking near a flowering plant of *Elleanthus longibracteatus* (**a, c**) and waiting to catch hummingbirds (**b**), that pollinate the orchid in Colombia. **C.** Changeable lizard, in a plant in Singapore. Sources: **A, C**, photographs by Dr. T. W. Yam; **B**, based on Ospina, 1969.

[2] Frogs in orchids. **A.** Frog in *Paphiopedilum* orchid. **B.** Cuban tree frog in *Vanda* flower. **C.** Frog in cowhorn orchid, *Cyrtopodium punctatum*. **D.** Frog among *Dendrobium* stems. **E.** Spotted yellow frog on *Dendrobium* leaf. Sources: **A, D, E.** Orchid Board (<http://www.orchidboard.com/community/advanced-discussion/46866-frogs-harmful-orchids.html>); **B,** courtesy *Key West Travel Guide* (<https://www.keywesttravelguide.com/>); **C,** National Park Service, U. S. Government (<https://www.rawpixel.com/image/4029436/frog-cowhorn-orchid>); National Park Service, U. S. Government (<https://www.rawpixel.com/image/4029436/frog-cowhorn-orchid>).

[3] Birds on *Grammatophyllum speciosum* near a pond in Singapore, which contains fish. **A.** Common kingfisher. **B.** Oriental magpie robin. Sources: Photographs by Dr. T. W. Yam.

snakes prey on them.

There is also one recorded case of an orchid, *Cymbidium serratum*, a terrestrial species found in the mountains of central and southern China, which is pollinated by a small rodent, *Niviventer fulvescens*, known as the chestnut white-bellied rat (Wang et al. 2008). However, a snake was not reported to visit this orchid.

In 1966, several years after he became the orang puti gila, the American spent six weeks in the Venezuelan jungle with the late Galfrid Clement Keyworth “Stalky” Dunsterville (1905–1988), coauthor with the late Leslie A. Garay (1924–2016) of the monumental *Venezuelan Orchids Illustrated* books (1959 et seq.). In addition to being an excellent artist, Stalky was a talented photographer and a good orchid grower who had paphiopedilums in his collection. One day he saw a small frog in the pouch of one of his plants and photographed it. He sent a copy of the photograph to the future orang puti gila with a question: “Did the frog fall in or jump in and, if the latter, why?”

The photograph is long lost, but a similar one is available (Fig. 2A). Unfortunately, there is still no definitive answer. Frogs may visit orchids to prey on insects, including pollinators, perhaps in search of water, possibly to find shelter, or maybe in an effort to hide by crouching in a pouch (Figs. 2D), or by blending with the flower (Fig. 2C).

A recently observed association

between orchids and birds in Singapore (Fig. 3A,B) is probably nonspecific and due to an accidental presence of a *Grammatophyllum speciosum* plant next to a pond. A kingfisher (*Ceyx erithaca*, Fig. 3A) and an oriental magpie-robin (*Copsychus saularis*, Fig. 3B) perch on the orchid and look into the pond. On seeing a fish in the water, they dive to catch it.

The flowers of *Grammatophyllum speciosum* are usually pollinated by *Megachile disjuncta* a solitary resin bee (Fig. 4A,B). Changeable lizards (*Calotes versicolor*, Fig. 1C), banded flower mantis (*Theopropus elegans*, Fig. 4C), praying mantis (*Stagmomantis* sp., Fig. 4D), shining leaf chafer beetle, *Mimela* sp. (Fig. 7A), and assassin bugs (Reduvoideae, Fig. 7B) all visit or hide near these orchids to prey on the various pollinators. Sometimes, they do catch a bee (Fig. 4E,F).

Spiders (Figs. 5A–D, 6A–D, 7C–E, 8A–D) are by far the most common predators; they hide or just position themselves in or near orchid flowers and give pollinators the last surprise of their lives by preying and feasting on them (Fig. 6C). Waiting in an *Orchis militaris* flower, a European species, (Fig. 5A) paid off with a meal (Fig. 5B) for the goldenrod spider, *Misumena vatia*. In North America, another yellow crab spider, *Thomisus callidus*, is waiting for prey on a rose pogonia, *Pogonia ophioglossoides* (Fig. 5C). Also in North America, a crab spider is hiding in the fold of the pouch of *Cypripedium acaule*

(Fig. 5D). Another example is a white crab spider, *Misumena vatia*, which caught a syrphid fly (family Syrphidae) on a purple orchid (Fig. 6D).

In Australia, the fringed mantis spider, *Portia* sp., hides in *Caladenia falcata* (Fig. 6A1,A2). The shiny jumping spider, *Cosmophasis umbratica*, was photographed on a flower of *Grammatophyllum speciosum* (Fig. 6C). Its excellent camouflage suggests that its presence in this flower is not accidental. In Madagascar, a *Panogena* moth (family Sphingidae) feeds, apparently oblivious to a spider that is probably stalking it (Fig. 7C), and a hawkmoth, *Coelonia brevis*, (Fig. 7E) was caught in midair by a spider (Wasserthal 1996, 1997).

In Indonesia, in about 1972–1974, the late Djunaidi Gandawijaja (died ca. early 2000) and the orang puti gila observed a barely visible spider web in front of *Dendrobium crumenatum* flowers. The web’s strands were so fine that they had to be made visible for photography by squirting (with a mouth) water on them. Unfortunately, the photograph is long lost (Fig. 8A) and the illustration here is an electronic reconstitution (an approximation). The late Jim Comber (1929–2005) photographed (1990) similar, almost-invisible spider webs on flowers of *Ceratochilus biglandulosus* in Java (Fig. 8B, yellow arrows). It would be interesting to determine if other Javanese spiders also construct almost invisible webs.

Two spiders in Colombia hide in flowers rather than construct webs (Ospina 1969). One such crab spider, *Epicadus heterogaster* (Fig. 8Cd), hides in the flowers of *Cycnoches chlorochilon* (Fig. 8Ca, blue arrows; Fig. 8Cb) and preys on pollinating euglossine bees, also known as orchid bees (Fig. 8Cc). A spider also hides in the labellum of *Epidendrum ciliare* (Fig. 8Da, 8Db, 8Dc, yellow arrows).

In Europe (Romania), the pollinators and other insect visitors to orchid flowers arouse interest of third-parties, animal that belongs to a different trophic level — the pollinators' predators (Heil 2008). In the temperate zone, the most common predators, which temporarily reside on orchid inflorescences, are various families of spiders (Araneae). Among these, the most common pollinators' predators are the crab spiders of the family Thomisidae, genera *Misumena*, *Thomisus*, *Xysticus* and *Diaea*.

The Thomisidae are also known as flower spiders or flower crab spiders due to the resemblance of their first two pairs of legs, which are longer and often held apart, ready to catch their prey similar to crab claws and to their ability to scuttle sideways or backwards when disturbed. They occur throughout the Northern Hemisphere; Europe, Asia, North America and North Africa (Whyte and Anderson 2017). In North America, they are known as goldenrod spiders, *Misumena vatia*, as they are most commonly found in goldenrods — bright yellow flowers that attract large numbers of insects, particularly in autumn.

Plants communicate simultaneously with the insects and the spiders via floral olfactory (scent), visual (color, shape), or tactile (texture) signals (Schaefer and Ruxton 2011; Schaefer et al. 2011). Flower-resident spiders have evolved to fine-tune on such signals and use them to their own advantage (Schiestl and Johnson 2013, Schiestl et al. 2011). They are attracted by flower odors and use visual and tactile cues for selecting hunting sites (Krell and Krämer 1998, Greco and Kevan 1994). Rather than passively and randomly selecting flowers to hunt on, crab spiders may identify floral signals aimed at pollinating insects, thus exploiting the signaling communication between the flowers and their pollinators (Chien

and Morse 1998).

Solitary ambush predators such as crab spiders are also known as sit-and-wait predators. Ambush strategies often rely on concealment, whether by staying out of sight or by means of camouflage (Théry and Casas 2002). Crab spiders use camouflage or cryptic coloration ("crypsis"), which is the ability to match their color with the background to perfectly conceal themselves and escape detection by other animals, especially of birds; their own predators (Chittka 2001, Brakefield 2009).

Crab spiders can mimic the colors of different flower species, allowing them to be cryptic in the color-vision systems of both avian predators and arthropod prey (Théry et al. 2004). This phenomenon, known as aggressive mimicry, is characteristic of the females of some genera, such as *Misumena* and

[4] Pollinators and predators on flowers of the tiger orchid, *Grammatophyllum speciosum*. **A.** *Grammatophyllum speciosum* pollinated by *Megachile disjuncta*. **B.** *Megachile disjuncta* carries pollinia of *Grammatophyllum speciosum* (black arrow with yellow lines on top). **C.** Banded flower mantis, *Theopropus elegans*, waiting for prey on the flower of *Grammatophyllum speciosum*. **D.** A praying mantis (blue arrow), *Mantis religiosa*, waiting for bees that pollinate the tiger orchid. **E.** Banded flower mantis, *Theopropus elegans*, caught a bee when it tried to pollinate the tiger orchid. **F.** A praying mantis (black arrow), *Mantis religiosa*, caught a bee when the latter visited the flower of a tiger orchid. All photographs by Dr. Tim Wing Yam.

Thomisus, which are able to change from white to yellow within 10 to 25 days while the opposite color change may take only about six days. The baseline color of the spider is white. However, depending on the color of the flowers they see around them — for example, a yellow flower — they can secrete a liquid yellow pigment into the body's outer cell layer. To return to the initial white color, the spider excretes the yellow pigment instead of storing it in its glands. Color changes are induced by visual cues and spiders adjust their body color according to their own color perception. Those with impaired vision lose this ability (Insausti et al. 2012). Nevertheless, the chromatic variation of Thomisidae is quite staggering. Their colors range from pure white (baseline color) to bright yellow (with red lateral stripes), orange, pink, purple, blue-turquoise, lime green to brown and black, and sometimes combinations of them. The males are smaller than females (sexual dimorphism) and have darker colors (color dimorphism).

Insects of completely different systematic groups, such as bees, moths and flies (Morse 1981), some of which differ in their color vision systems, are the prey of crab spiders. The most recent studies showed that crab spiders are not totally cryptic in the visual system of bees (a primary food source), in particular in the case of trained bees, which have learned to distinguish the shape and the movements of crab spiders at close range. Hence, even if the color match is not perfect, the coloration of the spiders may well blend in with the appearance of the inflorescence as a whole, as viewed from a large enough distance (Defrize et al. 2010).

Crab spiders are carnivores that capture or trap prey with their raptorial forelimbs (Schmalhofer 1999). They are formidable and patient hunters and usually remain motionless, waiting for the prey to come within reaching distance before lethally striking. Usually, they feed on invertebrate insects such as hymenopterans (ants, bees, wasps), dipterans (flies, mosquitos, gnats), lepidopterans (moths, butterflies) or coleopterans (beetles). They may also use nectar and pollen as food sources when prey is scarce (Wilcox 2017). In some cases, the insects may be several times heavier than their body weight. Large prey is immobilized by injecting the lethal venom from their strong, sharp fangs. Since they cannot chew, they use a particular type of external digestion by injecting a digestive

fluid containing different types of digestive enzymes (gastric juices) inside the bodies of the insects until the internal prey body become a viscous soup. The liquid is sucked out of the prey with their fangs until the crab is satiated. Ingestion of different types of prey determine the body coloration, especially for the chameleonic genera *Misumena* and *Thomisus*. For example, ingestion of red-eyed fruit flies, *Drosophila melanogaster*, causes the abdomen to turn pink (Schmalhofer 2000).

Thomisidae do not build webs to trap prey, though all of them produce silk for drop lines and sundry reproductive purposes. Males follow the draglines in search of potential mates.

In Central Europe, yellow crab spider females, *Misumena vatia*, temporarily inhabit the flowers of the lady slipper orchid, *Cypripedium calceolus* (Fig. 9A,C). The golden, inflated pouches of the orchids serve as a perfect camouflage for these masters of disguise, which prey on bee-mimicking flies and other small dipterans. Once the feast is finished, some of the empty fly carcasses are deposited inside the pouch (Fig. 9E). The lime-green crab spider, *Diaea dorsata*, with a brown mark on its back, is often seen hidden at the base of the dark-purple petals or on the slippery surface of the labellum (Fig. 9B,D). Smaller in size, it moves quickly and catches smaller forest flies, which constitute its main diet. After being devoured, they also end up thrown inside the golden grave.

Small lime-green crab spiders are often found in the subalpine forests residing on the whitish-pink flowers of the elusive phantom orchid, *Epipogium aphyllum* (Fig. 10A,B). Totally lacking chlorophyll, this orchid attracts small insects, like the small reddish-brown marsh flies, *Euthycera chaerophylli* (Fig. 10C), and forest flies, *Minettia lupulina* (Fig. 10D), with its bright translucent flowers and fermented-banana scent. Naïve and always in search of food, the small dipterans may fall victim to the crab spiders.

White female crab spiders, *Misumena vatia*, often reach large sizes by preying on large orchid pollinators. Camouflaged

- [5] Crab spiders and orchids. **A**. Yellow crab spider, *Misumena vatia* (black arrow) on *Orchis militaris*, the military orchid, in Europe. **B**. Goldenrod crab spider on *Orchis militaris* feasting on an *Andrena* female bee, a common pollinator of European orchids. **C**. Crab spider on Rose Pogonia, *Pogonia ophioglossoides*, in Canada. **D**. Spider hiding in the fold of the pouch of *Cypripedium acaule* in the USA. Sources: **A**, <https://pixabay.com/photos/crab-spider-flower-orchid-6269805/>; **B**, <https://pixabay.com/photos/spider-goldenrod-crab-spider-6256704/>; **D**, photograph by Tammy (no last name listed) on <https://www.pinterest.ca/pin/364017582351005218/?d=t&mt=login>.
- [6] Spiders and orchids. **A1, A2**. Fringed mantis spider on *Caladenia falcata* in Australia. **B**. Unidentified spider (cf. *Gasteracantha*) hiding behind the dorsal sepal of a purple orchid. **C**. The shiny jumping spider, *Cosmophasis umbratica*, perfectly camouflaged on the sepal of the tiger orchid, *Grammatophyllum speciosum*. **D**. White crab spider, *Misumena vatia* caught a syrphid fly on a purple orchid. Sources: **A1, A2**, <https://pixabay.com/photos/fringed-mantis-spider-orchid-4067408/>; **B**, spider <https://pixabay.com/photos/flower-orchid-spider-native-5581684/>; **C**, photograph by Dr. T. W. Yam; **D**, https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Misumena_vatia. (cf. – to be confirmed).

on a white common daisy, *Bellis perennis*, the female spider preys on a flesh fly of the family Sarcophagidae, which was pollinating *Anacamptis coriophora*, a nectar rewarding, bug-smelling orchid (Fig. 11A). A garden chafer beetle, *Phyllopertha horticola* (Family Scarabaeidae), was caught while pollinating the nectarless, purple flowers of the common spotted orchid, *Dactylorhiza fuchsii* (Fig. 11B). Beetles belonging to Scarabaeidae family are very efficient orchid pollinators.

It may seem strange, but, quite often, the white or yellow crab spiders choose to hunt on flowers that, to the human eye, do not appear to match in color. Because of their photoreceptors (that allow them to see ultraviolet, blue and green light), insects are mostly incapable of detecting the white or yellow spider on pink-purple flowers, perceiving it only as a dark shape against a dark background (Morse 2007). Therefore, for most insects, the white or yellow motionless spiders are virtually invisible on purple, red or dark-red flowers.

On the pink-purple flowers of *Dactylorhiza fuchsii*, a white female crab spider is devouring a dagger fly of the family Empididae, for which the spider was virtually impossible to be detected (Fig. 12A). Empididae are true pollinators of many species of *Dactylorhiza* species, inhabiting the swampy areas where these orchids occur.

A yellow female crab spider, with prominent lateral red stripes, resides on a purple inflorescence of the same orchid species. In the USA, these *Misumena vatia* females are called the red-spotted crab spiders (Fig. 12B). The presence of the red lateral stripes is genetically inherited and not influenced by the type of food consumed by the spider. Another yellow female hides camouflaged inside the pinkish flowers of the rare, nectarless, butterfly orchid, *Anacamptis papilionacea* (Fig. 12C), waiting for its prey — bees and small flies. A common honeybee, *Apis mellifera*, was just caught by a yellow female while pollinating the heath-spotted orchid, *Dactylorhiza maculata* (Fig. 12D). On a purple, three-toothed orchid, *Neotinea tridentata*, a yellow *Misumena vatia* just caught a longhorn beetle of the genus *Cortodera* (family Cerambycidae). Cerambycidae beetles are frequent pollinators of European orchids (Fig. 12E). Crab spider females often hesitate to catch much bigger and stronger insects like bumblebees, which are quite capable of stinging them. On a purple *Dactylorhiza maculata* inflorescence, a yellow female

retreats while trying to attack a large bumblebee, *Bombus sylvestris*, which, totally unaware of the spider, buzzes its wings and flies away, after pollinating the orchid (Fig. 12F). Bumblebees are large and powerful insects, rarely attacked by spiders due to their large size and stinging habits. However, when caught, they constitute a significant meal for the spiders.

Thomisus onustus crab spiders are also often found residing on orchid flowers. The females, which are much larger than males, can change their colors from white to yellow, pink, blue or combinations of these. Due to the

[7] Predators and pollinators. **A.** Shining leaf chafer beetle, *Mimela* sp., on a flower of *Grammatophyllum speciosum*. **B.** Assassin bug on a flower of the tiger orchid. **C.** *Panogena lingens* moth feeding on flowers despite the presence of a huntsman spider of the family Sparassidae, which is stalking it. **D.** A humorous cartoon of a pollinator encountering an unpleasant surprise on a *Cynoches* orchid. **E.** *Xanthopan sphinx* moth, caught in midair by a spider. Sources: **A, B**, photographs by Dr. T. W. Yam; **C, E**, photographs by Prof. L. T. Wasserthal, 1996, 1997. **D**, a no-longer-remembered artist.

reduced insect visual spectrum (most insects lack the red photoreceptors and cannot see the color red), different chromatic variations of *Thomisus* females remain undetectable on the purple orchid flowers. A white *Thomisus onustus* female resides camouflaged on an early marsh orchid, *Dactylorhiza incarnata* (Fig. 13A). A yellow female crab spider waits motionless for its prey on *Dactylorhiza maculata* inflorescence (Fig. 13B). A young female transitioning from greyish-blue to pink, rests on the purple pyramidal orchid, *Anacamptis pyramidalis* (Fig. 13C). A rare pink female, totally concealed on the purple inflorescence of the pyramidal orchid, waits for its victims (Fig. 13F). A white female *Thomisus* spider just caught a common honeybee, *Apis mellifera*, a pollinator of the pyramidal orchid (Fig. 13D). A careless nine-spotted moth, *Amata phegea*, is chased by a female spider, which was hidden inside the inflorescence of the *Anacamptis pyramidalis* orchid. Moths are a major addition to the spiders' diets, but also important pollinators of the pyramidal orchids (Fig. 13E). On another inflorescence, a white *Thomisus onustus* female is feeding on a common honeybee, *Apis mellifera*, while a nine-spotted moth, *Amata phegea* (Fig. 13G,) and a drone fly, *Eristalis tenax* (Fig. 13H), keep probing the nonrewarding flowers for nectar, totally ignoring the danger. Drone flies, like *Eristalis tenax*, have been shown to have the lowest reaction to the presence of spiders on orchids and, therefore, are some of spiders' most frequent victims (Brechtbühl et al. 2010).

Within the large variety of flower crab spiders, the genus *Xysticus* is widespread in Europe. They are smaller, sturdier and not so brightly colored, their nuances ranging from reddish-brown, brown and dark brown to black, resembling earth in color and texture. Nevertheless, brown and black colors constitute a great camouflage against whitish-pink or purple flowers, since they also appear dark on dark backgrounds, virtually invisible to most insects.

In the marshes of Eastern Europe during the hot summers, these predators may be seen hidden within the inflorescences of orchids or just waiting patiently to ambush their visitors. On a swamp-loving orchid, *Dactylorhiza maculata*, a rare black female *Xysticus* spider just caught a bee-mimicking fly, *Syrphus ribesii* (Fig. 14A). Hoverflies are capable of partially distinguishing brightly colored crab spiders, but black forms are almost undetectable in their

visual spectrum. A reddish-brown younger female just caught a small marsh beetle, on a neighboring *Dactylorhiza maculata* orchid (Fig. 14B). A brownish, earth-colored female devours with its venomous fangs a flower chafer beetle, *Tropinota hirta*, caught on an *Anacamptis morio* inflorescence (Fig. 14C). Chafer beetles are often found on orchids and are efficient pollinators of the temperate species. A mars dagger fly of the genus *Empis* was caught by a hungry *Xysticus cristatus* female crab spider. While holding on to the immobilized, paralyzed body of the insect, the spider stares for a moment at my gradually approaching camera. She gives me one last look before dragging her prey inside the inflorescence (Fig. 14D).

Another large, black female *Xysticus* is patiently waiting at the base of the inflorescence of *Dactylorhiza maculata* orchid (Fig. 15A). Brownish-colored, medium-sized females may also be encountered on purple orchids such as *Anacamptis coriophora* (Fig. 15B), also on the rare orchid hybrid, *Anacamptis × gennarii* (*morio* × *papilionacea*) (Fig. 15C) or on the beautiful, imposing *Anacamptis palustris* subsp. *elegans* (Fig. 15D). On dark-purple flowers, the brown *Xysticus* females are perfectly camouflaged, like

[8] Spiders that prey on orchid pollinators and their webs. **A.** Spider web in front of a *Dendrobium crumenatum* in Indonesia. The view is from behind the flowers with the web in front of them. This is an electronic recreation of a long-lost photograph taken at the Bogor Botanical Gardens in Indonesia, ca. 1972, by the late Dr. Djunaidi "Adjun" Gandawijaja (who squirted water on the nearly invisible web with his mouth to make it visible for photography) and Dr. J. Arditti. Upper right corner: flower of *Dendrobium crumenatum* with a pollen-bearing pollinating bee (**yellow a**). **B.** Barely visible spider web strands (marked with yellow arrows) around a flower of *Ceratochilus biglandulosus*. **C.** *Epicadus heterogaster* spider (open blue arrow in **a, d**), which hid in the labellum of a *Cycnoches chlorochilon* flower (**b**) and caught a euglossine bee (**blue wedge, c**). **D.** Spider hiding in the labellum (yellow arrows in **b**) of a flower of *Epidendrum ciliare* (**a, b**) and enlarged (yellow arrow in **c**). Sources: **A, D.** Gandawijaja and Dr. Arditti; **Aa,** Greg Alikas, American Orchid Society. **B, J. B.** Comber; **C, D,** based on Ospina, 1969.

dark patches on dark flowers.

Besides the spectacular Thomisidae family of crab spiders, European orchids are frequently inhabited by various other families of spiders that take great advantage of the main feature of the orchids' flowers: that of being a true magnet for pollinators. Despite their multitude, few species of spiders (other than crab spiders) have ever been photographed on temperate orchids, although there are some examples of those rare encounters.

Female orb-weaver spiders, *Gibbaranea bituberculata*, are often seen ambushing naïve pollinators on early spring orchids, like the harlequin orchid, *Anacamptis morio* (Fig. 16A). A slender crab spider of the genus *Tibellus* uses its dark-brown color to conceal itself on the flower stem and stalk a common blue butterfly, *Polyommatus icarus*, which just landed on the purple flowers of *Anacamptis palustris* subsp. *elegans* (Fig. 16B). In the cool, dark forests, a philodromid crab spider of the genus *Philodromus* hunts forest flies on the bird's-nest orchid, *Neottia nidus-avis* (Fig. 16C). This orchid, which entirely lacks chlorophyll, secretes large amounts of nectar on its labellum and attracts lots of foraging insects, constituting a great residence for the ambush predators. On the greater butterfly orchid, *Platanthera chlorantha*, a cobweb spider, *Theridion pictum*, hunts dagger flies of the family Empididae (Fig. 16D). Despite its smaller size, this spider can catch much larger prey with the help of its web, which immobilizes the insects. Subsequently, they are attacked and paralyzed with its venom. A slender crab spider, *Tibellus oblongus*, stalks small swamp flies on Schur's narrow-leaved marsh orchid, *Dactylorhiza traunsteineri* subsp. *schurii* (Fig. 16E). Small crab spiders of the genus *Philodromus* are found on high-altitude orchids like the false musk orchid, *Chamorchis alpina*, considered to be the smallest European orchid, reaching only 1.2–2.0 inches (3–5 cm) in height. *Philodromus* crabs hide between the minute flowers (0.08–0.2 inches [0.2–0.5 mm] in length), and prey on small flies that, while foraging for nectar, eventually pollinate them (Fig. 16F). Higher-altitude spiders such as the nursery web spider, *Pisaura mirabilis*, use *Anacamptis morio* inflorescences as hunting sites (Fig. 16H). In the southeastern part of Europe within the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve (southeastern Romania), *Mangora acalypha*, an orb-weaver spider, hides

inside the flower helmet of the monkey orchid, *Orchis simia* var. *albiflora* (Fig. 16G), or builds thin, almost invisible webs on *Anacamptis coriophora* inflorescences to trap insect pollinators attracted by the strong bug smell of the orchid (Fig. 17A).

The Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve is home to a wide variety of rare orchids such as the lizard orchid, *Himantoglossum calcaratum* subsp. *jankae*, which is often the residence of the lynx spider, *Oxyopes lineatus* (Fig. 17G). These ambush-hunting spiders do not trap their prey in webs but paralyze their victims with their venomous fangs (“chelicerae”). Often, they are seen feasting on the nine-spotted moth, *Amata phegea* (Fig. 17G), or on hoverflies such as *Syrphus ribesii* caught on *Anacamptis pyramidalis* inflorescences (Fig. 17B). In southern Europe, the jumping spider, *Pellenes seriatius*, with a bright-red mask on its eyes, is hiding behind the flower stem of *Neotinea tridentata* waiting for small insects to visit the orchid (Fig. 17C). In subalpine regions, the long-jawed spider, *Metellina mengei*, resides inside the yellow inflorescence of the pale-flowered orchid, *Orchis pallens* (Fig. 17D). The thread-weaver spider of the genus *Linyphia* uses its web to catch small dipterans that pollinate the common twayblade orchid, *Neottia ovata*, now in its fruiting stages (Fig. 17E). Aggressive oak spider females, *Aculepeira ceropegia*, inhabit various orchids such as *Dactylorhiza maculata* (Fig. 17F) or *Anacamptis morio* (Fig. 17H) where they ambush larger prey such as bees, bumblebees or bee-mimicking hoverflies, the usual pollinators of these orchids.

Toward the end of the summer during rainy days, salamanders may be encountered foraging the humid forests floors in search of food. They are opportunistic predators and feed on almost any organism of a suitable size, such as earthworms, flies, beetles, beetle larvae, moths, spiders, grasshoppers and mites. They may be seen passing by small groups of *Epipogium aphyllum*, since both the orchids and the salamanders prefer to live around small ponds or clear-water streams (Fig. 18D). The banana-scented orchid attracts many forest dwellers, such as capsid bugs of the Miridae family (Fig. 18A), forest black scavenger flies *Minettia lupulina* (Fig. 18B) or, quite often, hoverflies, *Meliscaeva cinctella* (Fig. 18C), that constitute a significant part of the amphibian’s diet. At times, it may be possible that this opportunistic predator may catch some of the small insects attracted by the scented orchids.

- [9] Crab spiders hunting, camouflaged on the golden pouch of the lady slipper orchid, *Cypripedium calceolus*. **A.** and **C.** Yellow female crab spider, *Misumena vatia*, stalking prey, camouflaged on the yellow orchid’s labellum. **B.** and **D.** Lime green crab spider female, *Diaea dorsata*, hunting small, forest flies on the lady slipper orchid. **E.** Small *Syrphid* flies (Dipterans) deposited inside the orchid’s pouchlike labellum, after being preyed on by the resident crab spiders. Photographs by Nora Angheliescu.
- [10] Phantom orchid, *Epipogium aphyllum*, and its temporary resident, small crab spider, *Diaea dorsata*. **A.** *Diaea dorsata* hiding behind *Epipogium aphyllum* flowers. **B.** *Diaea dorsata* getting into the attack position after sensing a *Minettia lupulina* fly (arrow) landing on the inflorescence. **C.** *Euthycera chaerophylli* fly visiting the flowers of *Epipogium aphyllum*. **D.** *Minettia lupulina* fly foraging for nectar on the inflorescence of the phantom orchid. Photographs by Nora Angheliescu.
- [11] Crab spiders preying on orchid pollinators. **A.** White female crab spider (white arrow) *Misumena vatia* hunting flies of the family Sarcophagidae, the pollinators of the bug orchid, *Anacamptis coriophora*. **B.** Female *Misumena vatia* feeding on the garden chafer beetle, *Phyllopertha horticola*, a common pollinator of the common spotted orchid, *Dactylorhiza fuchsii*. Photographs by Nora Angheliescu.

During autumn, another fierce predator, the European mantis, *Mantis religiosa*, becomes active. Also known as the praying mantis, a name derived from the praying position of the front (raptorial) legs that resemble a praying attitude, these large, powerful insects are carnivorous ambush predators that scan their surroundings and prey on most insects that are not too large to be captured by rapid extension of their raptorial legs. Only living and moving prey is captured and consumed immediately

using their powerful mandibles (Roeder 1935). The brown mantises also use active camouflage, by changing their color to match the color of autumn — dried, brown grass burned by the hot summer sun. Mantises most actively feed during September and October when the females form and deposit their eggs (“ootheca”). Since healthy offspring always depend on good food intake, female mantises are sometimes seen hanging motionless on the autumn lady’s-tresses orchids, *Spiranthes spiralis*, the last European

[12] Crab spiders adapt their colors to various orchid flowers. **A.** White female crab spider *Misumena vatia* on *Dactylorhiza fuchsii* inflorescence, preying on a dagger fly of the family Empididae. **B.** Yellow female crab spider *Misumena vatia* with lateral red stripes, residing on *Dactylorhiza fuchsii*. **C.** Yellow female *Misumena vatia* hiding inside the flower of the butterfly orchid, *Anacamptis papilionacea*. **D.** Yellow female crab spider *Misumena vatia* catching a common honey bee, *Apis mellifera*, a pollinator of the heath spotted-orchid, *Dactylorhiza maculata*. **E.** *Misumena vatia* feeding on a longhorn beetle of the genus *Cortodera*, on a three-toothed orchid, *Neotinea tridentata*. **F.** Whitish-yellow female crab spider *Misumena vatia* hunting a large bumblebee, *Bombus sylvestris* on *Dactylorhiza maculata*. Photographs by Nora Angheliescu.

[13] Rare chromatic varieties of crab spiders females, *Thomisus onustus*. **A.** White female residing on early marsh-orchid, *Dactylorhiza incarnata*. **B.** Yellow female hunting on *Dactylorhiza maculata* inflorescence. **C.** Rare chromatic combination of blue, pink and white of a *Thomisus onustus* female residing on the pyramidal orchid, *Anacamptis pyramidalis*. **D.** White crab spider female preying on a common honey bee, *Apis mellifera*, pollinator of the pyramidal orchid. **E.** Aggressive crab spider female chasing a nine-spotted moth, *Amata phegea*, a frequent pollinator of *Anacamptis pyramidalis*. **F.** Rare pink female, *Thomisus onustus*, camouflaged on a pink pyramidal orchid inflorescence. **G.** Crab spider feasting on a common honeybee, *Apis mellifera*, while a nine-spotted moth, *Amata phegea* forages for nectar on the inflorescence of *Anacamptis pyramidalis*. **H.** Drone fly, *Eristalis tenax* foraging for nectar on the same *Anacamptis pyramidalis* inflorescence. Photographs by Nora Angheliescu.

[14] Crab spider females of the genus *Xysticus* hunting orchid pollinators. **A.** Rare black crab spider female *Xysticus* feasting on a bee-mimicking fly, *Syrphus ribesii*, a frequent pollinator of *Dactylorhiza maculata*. **B.** Crab spider preying on small beetles, on a *Dactylorhiza maculata* inflorescence. **C.** *Xysticus* female feasting on a flower chafer beetle *Tropinota hirta*, on *Anacamptis morio* inflorescence. **D.** Hungry *Xysticus cristatus* female crab spider injecting venom into a dagger fly of the genus *Empis*, a pollinator of *Dactylorhiza maculata* orchid. Photographs by Nora Angheliescu.

[15] *Xysticus* crab spiders females residing on orchids. **A.** Rare black *Xysticus* female hunting on *Dactylorhiza maculata* inflorescence. **B.** Female crab spider residing on an *Anacamptis coriophora* inflorescence. **C.** Female spider hiding behind a flower of the rare naturally occurring orchid hybrid, *Anacamptis × gennarii* (*A. morio* × *A. papilionacea*) or Gennari's *Anacamptis*. **D.** *Xysticus* female hunting on *Anacamptis palustris* subsp. *elegans*. Photographs by Nora Anghelescu.

[16] European spiders hunting orchids' pollinators. **A.** Orb-weaver spider, *Gibbaranea bituberculata* camouflaging itself on the green-winged or the harlequin orchid, *Anacamptis morio*. **B.** Slender crab spider of the genus *Tibellus* stalking a common blue butterfly, *Polyommatus icarus*, on *Anacamptis palustris* subsp. *elegans* inflorescence. **C.** Philodromid crab spider of the genus *Philodromus*, hunting forest flies on the bird's-nest orchid, *Neottia nidus-avis*. **D.** Cobweb spider, *Theridion pictum*, hunting dagger flies of the family Empididae, on the greater butterfly-orchid, *Platanthera chlorantha*. **E.** Slender crab spider, *Tibellus oblongus*, stalking small flies on Schur's narrow-leaved marsh orchid, *Dactylorhiza traunsteineri* subsp. *schurii*. **F.** Philodromid crab spider of the genus *Philodromus* preying on high-altitude, small flies (Dipterans), frequent pollinators of the false musk orchid, *Chamorchis alpina*. **G.** Orb-weaver spider, *Mangora acalypha*, hiding inside the flower helmet of the monkey orchid, *Orchis simia* var. *albiflora*. **H.** Nursery web spider, *Pisaura mirabilis*, hunting on *Anacamptis morio* inflorescence. Photographs by Nora Anghelescu.

[17] Various European spiders hunting on orchids. **A.** *Mangora acalypha* spider hanging on its web, hunting on *Anacamptis coriophora* inflorescence. **B.** Lynx spider, *Oxyopes lineatus*, feeding on a hoverfly, *Syrphus ribesii*, caught on *Anacamptis pyramidalis* inflorescence. **C.** Jumping spider, *Pellenes seriatus*, waiting for small Dipterans behind the flower stem of *Neotinea tridentata*. **D.** Rare long-jawed spider, *Metellina mengei*, hiding inside the yellow inflorescence of the pale-flowered orchid, *Orchis pallens*. **E.** Thread-weaver spider of the genus *Linyphia* feasting on small Dipterans caught in its web built on the common twayblade orchid, *Neottia ovata*. **F.** Oak spider, *Aculepeira ceropegia*, hunting on *Dactylorhiza maculata* inflorescence. **G.** Lynx spider, *Oxyopes lineatus*, feeding on a nine-spotted moth, *Amata phegea*, on the lizard orchid, *Himantoglossum calcaratum* subsp. *jankae* inflorescence. **H.** *Aculepeira ceropegia* female spider hunting on *Anacamptis morio* inflorescence. Photographs by Nora Anghelescu.

[18] Salamanders passing in the neighborhood of banana-scented *Epipogium aphyllum*. **A.** Capsid bug of the Miridae family, rests on *Epipogium aphyllum* flower. **B.** *Minettia lupulina* fly foraging for food on phantom orchid inflorescence. **C.** Hoverfly, *Meliscaeva cinctella*, foraging for nectar on the labellum of the phantom orchid. **D.** Fire salamander, *Salamandra salamandra*, forages for small insects/flies around a group of the fermented-banana scented *Epipogium aphyllum* orchids. Photographs by Nora Anghelescu.

[19] Praying mantises and their insect preys, on the autumn lady's-tresses orchids, *Spiranthes spiralis*. **A.** Jersey grasshopper, *Euorthippus declivus*, resting on *Spiranthes spiralis* inflorescence. **B.** Grasshopper, *Chorthippus dorsatus*, foraging for food on *Spiranthes spiralis* flowers. **C.** Southern green stink bug, *Nezara viridula* f. *torquata*, foraging on *Spiranthes spiralis* inflorescence. **D.** Seven-spotted ladybug, *Coccinella septempunctata*, resting on *Spiranthes spiralis* flowers, after the storm. **E.** Common sailor butterfly, *Neptis hylas*, resting on the spiral orchid. **F.** European mantis male, *Mantis religiosa*, waiting for insect visitors to land on *Spiranthes spiralis* inflorescence. **G.** Praying mantis female hiding motionless, behind the inflorescence of the spiral orchid, waiting for its prey. Photographs by Nora Anghelescu.

orchid to flower (Fig. 19G). Much more mobile than the females, male mantises also hunt on the autumn lady's-tresses orchids keeping still in their praying position. However, when, suddenly, a large object approaches (my camera), they aggressively spread and buzz their enormous wings, trying to intimidate the intruder (myself; Fig. 19F). *Spiranthes spiralis* is a nectar-rewarding orchid with a pleasant vanilla sweet scent, which attracts a wide variety of insects such as grasshoppers (the preferred mantis food), *Euchorhippus declivus* (Fig. 19A) or *Chorhippus dorsatus* (Fig. 19B); bugs like the green stink bug, *Nezara viridula f. torquata* (Fig. 19C) and the seven-spotted ladybug, *Coccinella septempunctata* (Fig. 19D); and butterflies like the common sailor butterfly, *Neptis hylas*, all foraging for the last meal before the coming winter settles in.

Lastly, the deceiving orchids, so famous for stealing other plants' pollinators, have found their match: the ingenious, orchid spiders, masters of disguise and camouflage, which, in turn, exploit the orchids by hunting and feeding on their visitors and pollinators alike.

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Dedication

Professor Joseph Arditti dedicates his contribution to this article to Dr. Edward Chin.

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